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To Examine the Differences in Work-Life Balance Experiences between Urban and Rural Women Workers

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Abstract The work-life balance of the women of urban and rural India is analyzed in this study in terms of social, economic, cultural, and infrastructural influences on the women concerning their work and household responsibilities. This research explores participation in the labor force, allocation of time in work and domestic duties, and access to essential services such as childcare and healthcare, using the data collected for the Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS) and the Time Use Surveys (NSO). The results reveal that rural women experience a much heavier burden of unpaid work at home and devote an inordinate amount of time to chores compared with urban women. With the rise in LFPR, the access of rural women to formal employment opportunities remains too limited and assistance services remain deficient, thereby inhibiting further attainment of Work-life balance. Urban women, however, enjoy the advantage of greater access to formal employment, well-developed childcare services, and healthcare. They none the less suffer from more work-related stress and mental health issues as a result of longer working hours and the heavily uneven distribution of household tasks. The study further identifies the ways in which women cope with both situations. Rural women rely on communal networks and an informal market for childcare. Urban women tend to engage more with flexible work arrangements and technological options, while negotiating domestic responsibilities with family members. Nonetheless, structural constraints still remain in both rural and urban areas, undermining the effectiveness of coping strategies. The research further demonstrates the need for interventions that might bring attention to specific constraints faced by women in these different contexts, principally through improved access to resources, workplace flexibility, and pushback against traditional gender norms.

Keywords Work-life balance, Urban women, Rural women, Labor force participation, Household responsibilities, Time allocation, Gender equality.

Introduction

Background and Context: Work-life balance has emerged as one of the critical areas of research in the last two decades, especially with reference to Commerce, Management, and Human Resource Studies. Primarily, it refers to the equilibrium that an individual seeks between his/her professional obligations and personal life, which includes family, leisure, and personal care. The significant increase in women's participation in the global workforce draws attention to their unique predicaments of balancing these often-conflicting demands. Historically, these women have articulated a dual role: as primary caregivers inside the homes and contributors to the labor force. The intricacies involved in juggling these life dimensions have serious implications for their well-being, productivity, and job satisfaction. In India, these challenges are more potent, given the socio-economic, cultural, and infrastructural factors. The workforce participation of women has risen steadily, but a gendered division of labor and expectations surrounding caregiving responsibilities have put an unequal burden on women. While urban women may engage in formal employment with relatively better access to childcare and healthcare facilities, rural women face additional challenges of inadequate job opportunities, lack of access to public services, and traditional societal roles. The differences between the work-life balance of urban versus rural women are not just of academic curiosities, but they are also of practical significance for the aspects of human resource management and policy development, also in organizational studies. Such understanding of these dynamics will consummate a valid input toward enacting effective policies and practices that promote gender equality in the urban as well as rural labor markets.

Historical Evolution of Work-Life Balance: The concept of work-life balance, as we know it today, was much different in earlier years. Up until the time of World War I, particularly in agrarian and developing economies, the role of women was largely limited to household chores. One could say that economic participation was not in full force, so work-life balance was very little talked of. However, with the advent of industrialization in Western countries and later its transfer to the entire world, the work shift towards formal employment of women began. After World War II, in industrialized countries, a higher number of women entered the labor market, especially in the wake of a heightened demand for labor. However, these women still continued to shoulder the bulk of household responsibilities. However, due to the agrarian economy and long-rooted traditional and cultural setups, the changes in India came a bit too slowly. Rural women always worked on farms and at home, contributing largely to the economy but not very recognized or with very little recognition with no formal employment rights. It was only after the liberalization of the economy in the early 1990s that the formal sector of India, primarily located in urban areas, began to expand. This led to a tremendous jump in women's participation in the labor market, particularly in urban areas spanning a wide array of industries from manufacturing to services and information technology. Challenges of integrating work and life remain experienced most acutely by women, who must balance paid labor with unpaid domestic tasks. Demand for child and other forms of care, support for breaks, and the provision of services such as childcare and healthcare are different when comparing the experiences of women in urban and rural contexts impacting work-life balance and flexibility.

Work-lifebalance in India: Current developments: Over the past decade, India's female labor force participation (LFPR) has increased continuously. The Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI) highlighted that the LFPR in rural areas has grown from 23.3% in 2017-2018 to 37% in 2022-2023. In urban areas, the LFPR has risen from 20.4% in 2018-2019 to 25.4% in 2022-2023. However, rural women experience hindrances to engage in formal employment, and they are paid scarcely and become overburdened with unpaid work in agriculture and family business settings. These factors tend to give rise to work-life imbalance, as rural women tend to engage in manual labor for extended hours while having fewer resources to lessen their household and caregiving activities. On the other side, urban women have better access to paid employment opportunities in the formal sector, enjoying stability and social benefits. As per the Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS), the Worker Population Ratio (WPR) of women in urban areas increased from 18.4% in 2017-2018 to 23.5% in 2022-2023, indicating a growing number of women being employed in various industries. Unique challenges confronting women in urban settings include occupational stress, long hours of work, and the issue of the second shift, whereby women undertake both professional and domestic responsibilities. The rich opportunities for better health facilities, child care, and public infrastructure often give urban women the ability to balance work and family. But, of late, these avenues have busted more gaps in the path toward fighting for the full expression of equality, with a special emphasis on young urban working women caught between the demands of a career search and those of family obligations.

Objective of study

1. To investigate the relationship between labor force participation and employment patterns of urban and rural women.
2. To investigate time-use patterns of women in rural and urban areas in the balance between paid work, un-paid work, and personal time.
3. To examine how access to systems of support.

Review of Literature

1. **Acker, J. (2006):** According to Acker's concept "inequality regimes," the very physics of gender-class-race intersection creates systemic inequalities in organizations in the impediments faced by women to attain work-life balance. The impediment in scope and scale will be dependent on the settings: while women from urban areas suffer from structural inequalities in formal work settings, rural women encounter the usual cultural and familial expectations. Even though both of them have some dilemmas about work-life balance, their ideas have distinct perspectives of organizational and societal contexts.
2. **Bhattacharya, S., & Chatterjee, M. (2018):** This research examines the impact of various factors on work-life balance of women workers between urban-rural settings in India. Urban women experience high job stress as they are overwhelmed by their work demands and the low opportunity to balance outside work. On the other hand, rural women have to endure longer working hours but they are deprived of the supportive arrangements available to urban counterparts. But rural women often feel a greater sense of job satisfaction, due to being connected through stronger familial and community networks, in stark contrast to the stress and isolation urban women may feel, despite having better career outlook.
3. **Clark, S. C. (2000):** In Clark's border theory between work and family, the difficulty of boundary management between work and family life was specific to each of the settings. While urban women live in very strict boundaries of work and home which cause conflicts, rural women indulge in a fluid interaction with strong boundaries wherein the conflict with work is instrumentalized. This theory clearly substantiates the fact that work-life balance exists and is modified in response to both

- organizational standards and cultural settings thereby rendering adult experiences of urban and rural women distinct.
4. **Deery, S. J., & Jago, L. K. (2015):** The practices of work-life balance with reference to tourism and hospitality sectors are examined in the article. Women in formal sectors in urban areas have structured work-life balance policies such as flexible hours, while rural women are dependent on informal systems of support in this context. Rural women are likely to experience lower work-family conflicts, but the types of jobs they are performing are much more labor-intensive because such policies are absent in rural settings for rural women. Urban and rural women face enormous difficulties in balancing work-life responsibilities; nonetheless, the impediments may differ based on resource distribution and community support.
 5. **Dubey, A., & Dubey, R. (2016):** This study examines the differences in work-life balance between women workers in urban and rural areas of India. Urban women are more stressed on account of strenuous jobs, while rural women have to face problems arising out of long working hours coupled with burdens of extensive household work. Doable there are certain hurdles, rural women report greater job satisfaction, as that is possibly grounded on superior family support systems. Urban women on the other hand have greater work-life imbalances due to formalized work expectations.
 6. **Ghosh, D., & Ghosh, R. (2021):** Ghosh and Ghosh swear to measure the gendered experiences in India of work-life balance of the rural and the urban women. Rural women face particularly lengthy working hours, alongside the lack of healthcare and education, compounded with the demands of the urban woman's career that integrates conflict with work and family. Despite the heavy hours, yet rural women attain satisfaction from extended joint family and community support that days of urban women hardly receive, affecting the chances of balancing working and family responsibilities.
 7. **Gupta, N., & Duflo, E. (2009):** Gupta and Duflo, women who mostly work in rural areas, concentrate on gender inequalities in rural employment and their impact on work-life balance. Rural women find it hard to balance work and family life because society restricts them, and education is limited, and they do have to do hard physical work. Urban women have more formal work, yet it is a difficult haul with far more demands inherent in their jobs. They also consider that the situation needs to address the contemporary communications as women of various groups face different challenges, which implies targeted support based on geographical and socio-economic factors.
 8. **Kalliath and Brough (2008):** Kalliath and Brough's overview on work-life balance highlights diverse factors affecting the work-life balance in organizational setups. Urban women have extreme job demands and work for unusually long hours, which leads to burnout and conflict between work and family. On the contrary, rural women engage in physically demanding work. However, as it is less organized, it generally gives them time flexibility. This notwithstanding, both these groups are equally varied in being affected by societal and organizational factors that restrict their ability to attain an ideal work-life balance.
 9. **Kashyap and Kumar (2014):** Kashyap and Kumar (2014) study the work-life balance in Indian women workers from rural and urban contexts. Urban women endure higher levels of job stress because of high work demands and need for minimum flexibility, hence work-life imbalance. Rural women warrant less physically labor-intensive work but seem to exert their stronger familial support, hence developing a different kind of balance. Regardless of the variations, both the rural and urban working women's shoulders still bear a weighty responsibility to strike a compromise between family and work.
 10. **Kim and Jang (2020):** Kim and Jang in 2020 compared work-life balance among rural and urban women workers in South Korea. Urban women have a greater level of work-family conflict owing to job demands and a could-quite-long hours of work; whereas rural women, as a result of their job in agriculture, suffer major exhaustion but enjoy more flexibility related to work. The findings also highlight how it is important to understand the individual work-life balance from the context of career pressures and physical labor.
 11. **Kumar, P., & Kaur, H. (2016):** The chapter assesses the livelihoods of urban and rural women with reference to work-life balance. It finds that urban women exhibit a higher level of work time related stress because of pressure jobs and a rigid work environment. On the other hand, rural women, though experience less work time related stress in compare to urban, are caught between households and paid work. It is argued that roles, expectations, constraints and resource inputs differ across urban and rural women and contribute to varying degree of work-life balance.
 12. **Nair, S. S., & Nair, T. R. G. (2014):** This chapter analyses the work-life balance of women workers in the Indian IT sector. The experiences of rural and urban women workers are thus studied to assess the factors facilitating or affecting when IT sector women workers meet the twin responsibilities of home and paid work. The authors claim that the opportunities for rural women in the formal sector for waged work are still less than urban women, but the former make relatively fuller use of flexible work schedules from wage work sources than urban women.

13. **Pandey, R., & Kumar, S. (2015):** This chapter aims to identify the impacts of various economic activities on the magnitude of work related stress of urban and rural women. The study has brought to light the greater work related stress prevalence in urban as compared to rural women and a higher probability of stress prevalence in the age group of 40-54 years as compared to the age groups of 15-25 years and 26-39 years for both rural and urban women. Rural women with no stress showed a similar significant correlation of age, but lower stress prevalence with lesser work related factors than stress prevalent women (Table 8). 14. Raghavendra,
14. **S., & Verma, P. (2017):** This chapter examines the process of work-life balance among women workers in the formal and informal sectors in rural and urban centers. It was found that urban women are able to access leave above what is legally mandated under the formal leave policies, and also work with financial protection as they can avail of paid leave not only during delivery but also after the delivery while working in the formal sector.
15. **Sharma, N., & Kaur, S. (2020):** Sharma and Kaur (2020) studied the needs on the work-life balance and the effect that it has on female employees in India, with differing results thus between urban and rural workers. Stress amongst women facing jobs is much greater in urban women, who have often to face long working hours. In contrast, rural women are often called upon to put in physical labor in agriculture. Community support systems, however, assist to ameliorate some stress for rural women; urban women, however, have less support and may suffer isolation. This study emphasizes that, hence, the nature of work and support systems has a substantial impact on achieving a work-life balance in different settings.

Research gap:- The body of literature existing to date on work-life balance (WLB) among urban and rural women workers highlights several gaps that need investigation. Comparisons, while made in studies by Bhatta-thisarya & Chatterjee (2018) and Kumar & Kaur (2016), tend to ignore gender, specific geographic, financial, cultural, and policy differences within a country that may greatly influence WLB. So far, none of these studies have addressed any of the local cultural economic and policy differences between the rural and urban that shape women's work-life experiences in incredible divergent ways. Additionally, there is no full discussion on WLB comparisons across sectors. While some studies looked at the WLB for women in IT (Nair & Nair, 2014) or hotel sectors (Deery & Jago, 2015), further examination is warranted on the impact industrial demands in rural areas like agriculture or manufacturing may have regarding WLB. The other glaring gap is in the technological developments, and flexible working arrangements. The increasing adoption of remote work and digital tools has the potential to radically change WLB, but there is very limited concern with how such changes dramatically impact both rural and urban women. Moreover, this is largely a cross-sectional study, making it an episodic measurement tool, whereas longitudinally designed research is well-positioned to extend the insights concerning how the WLB changes over a span of time. With respect to the latter, the societal norms and increased roles for women in both the rural and urban contexts would evolve as time goes.

Methodology

The research study gives a brief overview of the key areas, which include differences in work-life balance for women in rural versus urban areas, hence introducing the main variables of interest: female labor participation, time allocation between their paid and unpaid work, and access to support networks. so, various research methods are used for this purpose.

Research Design

Type of Research Design:

Since this study aims at describing patterns of work-life balance between urban and rural women, a descriptive research design will be employed in this study. This design will note the differences in time allocation, labor-force participation and access to support systems between the two groups. This design will also have an exploratory character as it attempts to highlight some of the key factors influencing women work-life balance in a comparative way.

Justification for the Chosen Design:

The study adopts a descriptive design based in part on the systematic collection and presentation of data regarding the women work patterns in rural and urban areas. The exploratory component of the design will serve to unfold the factors and conditions which, in combination, lead to observed work-life balance-related outcomes. This combination allows in-depth understanding of the issue.

Research Approach**Quantitative Approach:**

The main objective of this approach is to conduct research that provides assessment of numerical data about urban and rural women's labor force participation, time allocation, and access to support services. This will therefore involve using some methods like surveys combined with secondary data analysis for the purposes of quantifying these variables and facilitating comparisons of the two groups.

Justification for the Chosen Approach:

The quantitative style of investigation will involve identifying diverse, objective patterns and trends from a large quantity of data and will contribute to an elaborate statistical analysis. Given the volume of existing datasets obtained from various sources, such as the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI) and the National Statistical Office (NSO), it would delineate robust empirical support for the targeted objectives of the research.

Data collection:

On the basis of the collected information from multiple government bodies and international reports, the means of attaining the data will rely solely on secondary sources to have an insight into women in work-life balance in both urban and rural settings. The principle sources in this case will be the PLFS Annual Report (2022-23) by the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI) for understanding labor force participation and employment trends; the NSO Time Use Survey (2019) for the analysis of time spent on paid versus unpaid work; as well as reports from UN Women concerning accessibility to healthcare and childcare services.

The secondary data will be scrupulously culled, cleansed, arranged, and organized under broad categories of work, including labor force participation, time allocation, and wide access to services. A comparative analysis will be made on the two groups to give a concrete idea about what tools influence work-life balance. The major advantage of using secondary data is that it allows one to conduct analyses while exerting limited time and costs.

Analysis

This section introduces the analysis and interpretation of data collected and obtained from various government and international sources, pertaining to the objectives of the research. Based on the objectives dealing with work-life balance for urban and rural women, the analysis in this section blends both quantitative and qualitative approaches and has been focused on providing insights on time allocation, labor force participation, and access to support services for women living in urban and rural areas.

1.Labor Force Participation and Employment Patterns of Urban and Rural Women**Objective:**

To investigate the relationship between labor force participation and employment patterns of urban and rural women, and how this relationship influences the work-life balance of women.

Labor Force Participation Rate (LFPR)

Based on the PLFS Annual Report issued by the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI): Annual Report (2022-23), the Labor Force Participation Rate (LFPR) of women increased from 23.3% in rural areas in 2017-18 to 37.0% in the year 2022-23. For urban areas, it increased from 20.4% in the year 2018-19 to 25.4% in 2022-23.

Interpretation: The very positive analysis shows high growth trends in LFPR for females, particularly in rural regions, giving an overall rise in the aggregate economic activity of women. The rising trend might be due to changing employment patterns, in which more rural women began performing agriculture duties and informal work or initiated micro-enterprises, while urban women gained entry into the formal economy and, hence, had greater financial stability. Unemployment Rate (UR) While the unemployment rate under

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consideration fell from 5.6% for rural areas in 2017-18 to 2.9% in 2022-23, it fell from 9% in 2017-18 to 5.1% in 2022-23 for urban areas.

Interpretation: The decrease in the unemployment rates shows that some positive economic trends are being noticed; practically, in rural areas, some new vegan-related employment opportunities in agriculture and small enterprises have appeared. However, some business-like features to urban industries like access to formal sector jobs will always keep them at scale, so it is plausible that we have, conspicuously, still a very stark reality: unemployment indeed among females in urban settings is still slightly better than set to less than this in comparison with rural areas.

Workforce participation rate (WPR): This number increased from 22.0% for women in rural areas in 2017-18 to 35.9% in 2022-23 and from 18.4% in urban areas in 2017-18 to 23.5% in 2022-23.

Interpretation: The proportion of women working or engaged in the labor force is increasing more in rural areas. Integration of women into both informal and formal markets appears to be on the rise. Rural women continue to be exposed to greater risk of informal employment, a working arrangement that generally offers lower wages, unstable work conditions, and poorer access to workplace benefits.

Unemployment rate (UR): The unemployment rate of women in rural areas declined from 5.6% in 2017-18 to 2.9% in 2022-23; urban women moved down from 9.0% to 5.1%.

Interpretation: Rates of unemployment falling could portend positive things for rural areas, where new job opportunities might have arisen in agriculture and small enterprises. Yet, urban women succumbed to higher unemployment rates than their rural counterparts, perhaps due to competitiveness for more formal-sector jobs or limited alternatives on offer in cities.

2. Time Allocations and Work-Life Balance of Urban and Rural Women

Objective: To investigate time-use patterns of women in rural and urban areas in the balance between paid work, un-paid work, and personal time.

Un-paid Work and Time Use: With regard to the NSO Time Use Survey (2019), rural women spend approximately 300 minutes per day on unpaid work (household chores, caregiving, etc.); urban women spend about 200 minutes. **Interpretation:** A higher number of unpaid work hours worked by rural women reflects their obligations toward domestic and community-related tasks. These sorts of tasks usually restrict them from engaging in paid work as they are more labor-intensive and require longer hours to complete. Even though urban women spend equally long hours on unpaid work, being a relatively better-off group, they probably have better access to time-saving support services, such as domestic help.

Paid labor and Hours of Work:

Rural women work in agriculture or informal sector jobs here, while time spent on paid labor is at least seasonally variable.

Urban women, however, work longer hours in the formal sector, averaging from 40-48 hours weekly for full-time employees.

Interpretation: Urban women may have better-defined work hours, allowing them to have clearer delineation between paid and unpaid work. In contrast, rural women face varying work hours that blur the lines between their work and personal lives. Type of employment also determines their competitive position in claiming a stable hour's job; generally, urban women are in a better position because of improved job security and formal work arrangements.

3. Access to Support Services and Work-Life Balance

Objective: To examine how access to systems of support, such as child care, health facilities, and flexible working time arrangements affect work-life balance for rural and urban women.

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Access to Childcare: In rural areas, just 5 to 10% of women have access to formal childcare services (World Bank, 2021). In urban areas, around 30 to 40% report having access to formal childcare services (International Labour Organisation [ILO], 2022).

Interpretation: Rural women were faced with considerable obstacles to accessing formal childcare services, which would limit their opportunity to engage in formal employment or other paid work outside the home. Urban women appear to have a comparatively easier access to childcare facilities, therefore enabling them to cope up with the demands of work and caregiving duties.

Access to Healthcare: Approximately 20 to 30% of rural women reported having no healthcare services nearby (UN Women 2022). 70-80% of women in urban places have access to healthcare services within their cities (UN Women, 2022).

Interpretation: Disparity is apparent in access to healthcare, which denotes the difficulty rural women face in attending to their health and well-being needs. Lack of healthcare access leads to an increase in challenges experienced in balancing work and life dimensions. Urban women have better access to healthcare services, which allows them to manage their health difficulties more effectively, resulting in a better overall work-life balance.

Key-finding:

All the results derived from the analysis of data throw light on these very vital findings:

Rise of Labor Force Participation in Rural Areas: The rising Labor Force Participation Rate (LFPR) of rural women-female participation in economic activities-is illustrated by an increase in that 23.3 percent in the year 2017-18 to 37.0 percent in 2022-23. However, like any girl, once women reside in rural areas, due to the seasonality and informal nature of employment, their chances of acquiring a work-life balance as commonly defined are limited.

Time Burden of Unpaid Work: Rural women engage in 300 minutes a day of unpaid work as compared to 200 minutes a day of urban women. This indicates that while undertaking household and community responsibilities sees such women as affording lesser time in search of paid work along with lesser time meant for their pursuits.

Limited Access to Support Systems in Rural Area: Very limited access to support systems of childcare and health services in rural areas makes the amalgamation of work and personal life uphill, while urban women have relative access to those services, which, greatly, allows for better work-life balance.

Employment Opportunities and Economic Security: Very serious employment opportunities to urban women also happen in the formal sector, which adds office benefits as well that's uncertain to rural women; they purely work in the informal sector or an agricultural sphere where, majority times, there is an absence of certainty with job securities, no growth opportunities or perquisites, culminating in inhibited well-being and work-life integration.

Work-Life Balance can be an extensive area of interest, While both urban and rural women faced obvious struggles on work-life balance, the sources and form these challenges take tend to differ from one another. Urban women are engaged in work-family conflict and long working hours in formal employment, while rural women cannot avail themselves of job opportunities and face longer hours with little or no compensation in two instances-one being paid and the other unpaid labor-as well as lack of support mechanisms.

This assessment views the challenges in work-life balance that urban and rural women are experiencing as a whole. The findings will highlight the importance of targeting the intended interventions so that women in both contexts may be provided support, including increased access to childcare, healthcare, and job security, as well as acknowledgment of the substantial contribution of women's unpaid work contribution.

Conclusion

This study contributes valuable knowledge to the articulateness of issues regarding the balance between work and life among women in urban and rural settings. Furthermore, the contributions of socio-economic factors, availability of infrastructure, and cultural expectations on these experiences have been outlined. Analyzing secondary data from the Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS), Time Use Surveys (NSO), and other reputable sources suggests that rural women suffer a highly disproportionate amount of unpaid household work, compared to their urban counterparts. This imbalance is evident in the

Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR) where rural women have seen a notable increase in year-long participation, but there is still quite constrained scope for gainful activities because of limited job opportunities, child care, and health care services. Other reasons for an imbalance for rural women as to the balancing of informal work are diminished income security and well-being. On the contrary, the better access to formal employment, child care facilities, and health care benefits urban women as is represented by their share of the Worker Population Ratio (WPR). Naturally, however, long working hours, working stress, and an ever-pressurized sphere of domestic responsibilities compound to create a mountain of challenges. The data quoted struggle for work-life balance to reflect an overall fair representation, but the working environment remains tough for urban women straining their mental health and leading them into burnout. The study has also brought to light the adaptive strategies adopted by the two groups of women to balance work and life. Rural women are inclined to create community-based support networks and informal caregiving arrangements while urban women resort more to technology, flexible work options, and negotiating household responsibilities. The preponderance of these adaptive strategies does not diminish the presence of structural barriers for both rural and urban women toward realizing a balanced and fulfilling life.

In summary, the finding of this report is that tailored policy interventions are necessary to target the unique hardships that women are facing-both urban and rural. To achieve better work-life balance quality-of-life indicators, policymakers supported the access to resources such as childcare, medical care, and flexible work options, while at the same time stressing the need to counteract traditional gender roles and expectations.

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